

THE EFFECTS OF MUSIC EDUCATION IN PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATION ON COGNITIVE (MENTAL) DEVELOPMENT ON CHILDREN

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The Effects of Music Education in Preschool Education on Cognitive (Mental) Development on Children

Abstract

Ensuring that different tones of classical music can be accompanied by children under all circumstances, while children are playing by themselves, while breastfeeding or trying to feed them, is an effective element that enables the positive interaction of cognitive development and cognitive skills in preschool children.

It is observed that environmental and social harmony, together with happiness, is at a high level in children, whose standard life skills are colored with an effective musical that makes cognitive skills positive for the brain , and new environments are created.

In the 0-6 age period, when the child's brain development will complete 70% of his cognitive skills, it is very important to establish communication with the science of music in the first stage, but it is one of the most important factors that positively affect the cognitive development of individuals, after nutrition activity.

First of all, in the field of music science education, regarding the newly existing and developing science of music sociology, the texture of our country in the music medium, its music-sensitive environment, the music education institutions and the

relationship between the institutions, how they should be and what the existing problems are, It provides information on how to resolve and validate.

The sociology of music science actively intervenes and searches for solutions to such problems and produces solutions for their effective implementation.

Keywords: *Music, cognitive development, preschool education, child development, preschool music education, psychology, sociology.*

1. Introduction

The saying "Music is the food of the soul", which is known and approved by everyone, is not only true, but also approved by the branches of science. Listening to influential works in classical music such as Beethoven, Bach, and Mozart in infants and children close to infancy greatly contributes to the cognitive, psycho -motor and social-emotional development of children at this developmental age .

The sense of rhythm that babies feel emerges with music, providing movement to the baby, which accelerates the baby's psycho -motor skills.

The classical music that babies listen to has had positive effects on their positive emotions and faster growth.

Children who have a lot of musical activities in childhood gain a place in society as effective individuals who have developed themselves in adulthood and can look from a positive perspective.

Character and skills in childhood develop very effectively in children aged 0-3. Inclusion of classical music in the education of children in the 0-3 age group and making them sing songs is a very important activity for the first start.

Children at this age should be taught the rhythms in music practically, and telling should be in the background. Because children can repeat what they hear, in this case, they begin to develop their musical ear and musical memory.

Melodic activities , along with short notes that can be memorized in the accompaniment of any musical instrument, have a very important place in terms of physical development as well as cognitive development.

play a musical instrument enables our mind to constantly think and take an active role, and in this case, the mind provides continuous development.

The main reasons for the differentiation of the science of sociology into different branches and the reasons determined, the reasons why the science of sociology of music emerged specifically in a different field of sociology; The aim of this study is to investigate the problems of existing communities and how to solve these problems with music.

The science of sociology of music examines in detail the effects of musical activities on societies, not just the study of the problems that coexist with music.

However, the fact that studies in designated areas are specific to their own content awaits researchers' knowledge and interest in their specific field.

Music science, the new field of the sociologist who wants to do these studies, or the field of music science, which is considered individually, must have reached the knowledge, interest, manners and concept.

Thus, there are detailed study opportunities in studies that can go down to detailed details. The different kinds of studies carried out by the Social Scientists doing research enable sociology to adapt to the field of music science, to gain flexibility, to develop cognitive skills, to increase the knowledge and skills learned about the field of music science, and to create very effective thoughts.

The new situations that have arisen enable to open specialization areas in different fields related to music, and this situation creates a special sociology and sociology of music science.

Being able to read notes by taking musical notation education in childhood is as important as learning a different language.

Being able to play a new musical instrument makes great contributions to children and provides positive development. It has been observed that the student who can play the piano for a short time solves problems faster by producing more effective solutions for difficult problems than the children who did not play the piano.

Children have a variety of abilities and capacities. Some children's interests, some needs, some have the ability to play mixed musical instruments, some have the ability to play simple musical instruments.

1 a. Investigating the Problem

What are the effects of music education in preschool education on the cognitive development of children?

1.b. Determining the Purpose

The main purpose of the prepared thesis proposal is; A more comprehensive examination of music education in pre-school education, determination of the effect of musical education on children, the development of mental functions of the students who receive music education at a young age, the ability to use their musical education and editing skills for life, ensuring that children with a high level of imagination and editing skills can use their musical education. .

1.b.1.Sub-Purposes

1. What are the effects of music on the mental development levels of 3-4 year old preschool students?
2. Does the effect of music on the mental development levels of 3-4 year old preschool students differ according to gender?

1.c. Importance of the Subject

The contribution of the music education given in pre-school education to the development of the communication channels between the brain lobes of the individual will increase the individual's performance in all areas at the psychomotor and cognitive level and raise it to a higher level.

1.d. Determining Subject Definitions

Brain: a physical control center in the interior of the skull responsible for all electrochemical and neuronal actions.

we examine the definitions of the author Ahmet YILDIZ in the definitions about the brain and learning . “The brain receives stimuli from its environment through our five senses. He organizes these stimuli, researches what he wants to mean, then decides what to do.

1.e. Hypotheses Determined for the Thesis Study

It is thought that individuals who receive music education during pre-school education have a high level of success in their education life.

It is thought that students who are active in the field of music in pre-school education are more successful, more social, and solve problems more quickly and practically than students who are not active in the field of music.

What are the differences in the mental development stages of the students who are active in the field of music in pre-school education compared to the students who are not active in the field of music?

Music increases the development levels of preschool students in the 3-4 year old group.

1.f. Identified Limitation

This thesis study, which was carried out with the aim of better analyzing the thesis research data, was limited only to children in the pre-school education age group of 3-4 years old.

2. Research on the Subject

When the studies on the subject are examined, studies have been carried out in similar fields in many universities, and a very comprehensive research study was carried out by Gazi University/Gazi Education Faculty in 2002.

It has been observed that in all studies in this field, very valuable findings supporting the thesis proposal have been obtained and these data have been analyzed and evaluated.

In the thesis work to be done, the analyzes and evaluations supporting the thesis proposal will be comprehensively included.

The reason for the development of the sociology of music science in our country; The progress of the information in various fields, the effective analysis of the research results, the conclusion of the data are the result of the processing.

The first of several major disciplines, which are closely related to the sociology of music science and take a primary role in the correct analysis of the existing field, is the effect of Educational Sciences and Sociology of Music on cognitive development.

Although the concept of education has been fully examined in the literature in terms of its separate functions, it has been defined in this way.

It is a very old fact that the sociology of music science is used for therapeutic purposes. In the past, our ancestors used music as a treatment method for more than one disease.

Liberman stated that while various functions of education are being studied, there are factors that increase the mental (intellectiuel) development of the education unit, are orientation to a new job, and that there are constructive factors in the continuation of the communication skills with the development in the cultural theme. must be.

In this situation, the most preferred institution activities should not be one kind of intellectual , not only professional and only cultural, but all together.

Music education science was applied in various subject streams in the pre-school period, and they tried to examine the effect of students on cognitive achievement development related to the subjects.

When we look at the general aims of the music education programs in music education institutions in our society, we can see that new goals have been determined.

When we look at the music branch course application program of pre-school and kindergartens, where the sociology of music education is applied very intensively, the general objectives are as follows;

1. Providing the ability to understand and comprehend the importance of culture, tourism, art and music in the life of people and society,
2. Being able to explain one's own self more easily through music,
3. Gaining values education such as developing love, sharing, solidarity, empathy and sense of responsibility through the application studies of music science education programs ,
4. To be able to see and apply that the sociology of music science is an inseparable part of the culture in the society from the general culture,
5. Having a song memory that reinforces the national unity with the science of music and ensures being together with the global level,
6. Ability to use Turkish language efficiently, effectively and meaningfully in musical works with words ,
7. To be able to comprehend and express the place and importance of the sociology of music science in the life of the individual.
8. To be able to perceive, comprehend and apply Mustafa Kemal Atatürk's views on cognition, art and music science.

As a result of the studies, it was found that there was a significant increase in the success of the students, and the units explained with music were better understood and they provided permanent learning.

pre-school games with music on children was investigated by Labow and Sewell . Plays with music are left to the creativity and imagination of the students. The studies and methods while preparing the Musical Games were examined in the classroom on their own, in the form of several classes coming together.

As a result of all the studies, it has been determined that preschool children are quite successful and self-sacrificing in the musical play.

The basic principles regarding the implementation of musical drama studies in pre-school education in the institution are emphasized.

For this purpose, new situations have emerged by comparing the teaching of the pre-school 3-4 age group with the musical drama method and the teaching with the non-music drama method.

In the studies, the findings obtained after the experience and observations and the examination of the writings about the field were collected in a single pool, and it was determined that the student who was in the music science drama hour participated in the education-teaching process mentally, cognitively and socially-emotionally.

It has been concluded that in order to ensure the participation and continuity of children in the pre-school period with music science drama techniques, the methods and techniques should be used effectively, the application method should be correct and the principles related to the existing conditions should be applied properly.

The aim of the studies is to reveal the effectiveness of the drama method studies in the Drama Activities lesson, Let's play our emotions, in terms of success and interest and attitude towards the lesson, by comparing them with the central and village pre-school education institutions.

3. Determination of Methods

3.a. Determination of the Research Model

In the research, methods developed in the experimental field will be used in order to follow the cognitive (mental) development of the students who receive music education in the pre-school period and the cognitive (mental) development of the students who do not receive music education.

The research will be organized according to the semi-trial model, which is one of the trial models. The quasi-experimental model is the most used experimental design, especially in studies conducted in pre-school education institutions, when it is not possible to keep all variables under control (Cohen et al. Manion, 2000).

Half-trial models are used in many cases where the control of real trial models cannot be achieved or even, they are not sufficient (Karasar, 2008).

In addition, quasi-trial models are trial models used in many educational studies when it is not possible to determine schools and classes (Kerlinger, 1973).

This research will be supported by the unequaled control group model from the quasi-trial models. The unequaled control group model is very similar to the pretest - posttest control group design. However, the only and most significant difference between them is that the groups are formed randomly.

Looking at the model, no special effort is made to equalize them by neutral assignment. However, care is taken to ensure that the participants are of similar nature. Which of these groups will be the experimental group and which one will be the control group is determined by an unbiased selection (Karasu, 2008)? The appearance of the experimental design is given in Table 1:

Table 1: Experimental Design

Groups	pretest	Experimental Process	final test
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Experiment	scale	teaching with music	Scale
Control	scale	3–4-year-old preschool curriculum	scale

Control group testing

All activities are performed by a group of students at the beginning of the semester by listening to music. The activities are done by another group of students without listening to music. The effect of music on the mental and cognitive development of both groups is observed.

Then, at the end of the term, the effect of the difference in success between the two groups on mental development is measured by listening to music.

3.b. Determination of the Sample

The study group of the research will consist of students aged 3-4 years studying in a private school in the Bostanlı district of İzmir in the 2014-2015 academic year.

The school where the research will be conducted will be determined after teacher interviews. With the permission to be obtained from the İzmir Provincial Directorate of National Education, the schools will be visited, and the teachers will be interviewed.

The activities done in the experimental group are processed by the preschool teachers in line with the daily plans prepared by the researcher.

is expected to apply research-based learning activities for nine weeks in which “Concepts, Numbers, Shapes” in the 3-4 year old group are included .

For this reason, teacher voluntariness will be taken as a basis in the selection of the experimental groups.

3.b.1. Attitude Scale Towards Teaching Profession

Scale Towards Teaching Profession" will be prepared by the researcher in order to determine the attitudes and behaviors towards the teaching job of the candidates who want to be a preschool teacher . Four stages will be followed in the development process of the Likert -type scale.

In the first stage, a literature review will be conducted on the attitude development scale in order to identify the existing items. In addition, students' opinions about their attitudes towards the teaching profession will be taken.

In the second stage, expressions that can be used as attitude sentences will be determined from the sentences written by the teacher candidates. These expressions will be rearranged in accordance with the spelling rules necessary for the attitude.

At the stage of determining the requirements of the items, the literature on the stages of attitude scale development will be reviewed and the researches on attitude will be examined.

In the third stage, the corrected and rewritten attitude sentences, affective , cognitive, mental, social-emotional and behavioral components of attitudes towards the teaching profession will be taken into account.

While conducting these studies, care will be taken to ensure that the existing expressions are positive or negative, and that they are equal in number according to which theme they represent. Items with this shape; It will be presented to individuals who are experts in development, which is a psychological measurement tool, to evaluate it in terms

of language and scope. As a result of these evaluations, the items will be made ready for trial form.

In the fourth and last stage, the reliability and validity studies of the scale will be conducted after the trial application. Therefore, the most appropriate Cronbach's alpha coefficient for Likert-type scales is to calculate. (Tezbasaran, 1997). To determine validity, content validity and construct validity tests will be conducted.

3.c. Data Collection

In the study, data will be collected from the fourth-grade teacher candidates of Dokuz Eylül University Education Faculty Preschool Teaching in the second semester of the 2014-2015 academic year.

Before the experimental process, a teacher self-efficacy scale and a behavior and attitude scale towards the teaching profession will be made in both the experimental and control groups. After the experimental process, the teacher self-efficacy scale and the attitude scale towards the teaching profession will be applied again.

3.d. Analysis of Data

The data obtained within the framework of the general purpose of the research will be analyzed using the SPSS 15 program. In the research; The two-factor ANOVA test, which is used in repeated measurements, will be used to compare the changes in the self-efficacy and attitudes of preschool children in the experimental and control groups towards their ability to do the teaching profession from the first stage of the experiment until after the experiment.

The two-factor ANOVA technique, which is applied in single-factor repeated measurements, is used in the statistical analysis of experimental designs with pre-test and post-test control groups. (Buyukozturk, 2006).

In the light of all this information, no child should ever be left or abandoned in a quiet room or in an environment without music in the classroom.

Ensuring that different tones of classical music accompany children while they are playing by themselves, while breastfeeding or trying to feed them, is an important factor that will positively affect the brain development and cognitive skills of the preschool child.

Children whose daily life skills are colored by the right choice of music, which makes their brains and cognitive skills positive, and who are presented with new environments, become calmer, more harmonious and happier individuals.

It is very important to establish communication with the science of music at the first stage in the 0-6 age period, when the child's brain development will complete 70% of his cognitive skills, and it is a fact that it is one of the factors that will positively affect the intelligence development of individuals after nutrition activity.

4. Time Schedule and Determined Work

	2013-2014 Academic Year												
Transactions								03. 11	04. 11	05. 11	06. 11	07. 11	08. 11
Literature search													
Preparation of data collection tools													

Preparation of events and event plans													
Pre-trial studies of data collection tools													
Transactions	2014-2015 Academic Year												
	09.11.11	10.11.11	11.11.11	12.11.11	01.12.12	02.12.12	03.12.12	04.12.12	05.12.12	06.12.12	07.12.12	08.12.12	09.12.12
Literature search													
Obtaining application permission from relevant units													

Preliminary trials of activities												
Application of preliminary tests												
Experimental procedure												
Application of post-tests												
Analysis of Data												
Writing findings and comments												
Writing conclusions and recommendations												

Finalization of the thesis report														
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5. Conclusion

As a result of the examination of the researches; It has been determined that music education has a great effect and benefit in the cognitive (mental) and personality development of the individual.

This training is considered to be more active than individuals who do not have musical education and can use their mental skills at a high level.

As a result, the fact that music is highly determinative in social as well as personal terms, has different codes, and has sociological roots as well as individual.

emergence of the individual, cognitive, social , linguistic, psychological, psycho - motor, economic, social-emotional and self-care skills and cultural advantages of the sociology of music science to the child's life, the existing dimension in the child's education is at the first stage and is an indispensable part of educational practices. It has been an effective discipline as a whole.

While the sociology of music science was organized in the educational format, especially in our country, some problems arose due to internal and external reasons in the preparation, planning and implementation of music education practices, as well as in the relationship of education-teaching practices with other disciplines, and these problems have continued until now.

Some of these problems have been solved with educational practices and some with Gardner's Intelligence tests theory as a result of Waldorf education studies . In this sense, the findings of sub-stages such as sociology of educational science, philosophy of educational science, psychology of educational science and economics of educational science come into play.

First of all, in the field of music science education, regarding the newly existing and developing science of music sociology, the texture of our country in the music medium, its music-sensitive environment, the music education institutions and the relationship between the institutions, how they should be and what the existing problems are, It provides information on how to resolve and validate.

The sociology of music science actively intervenes and engages in novel studies that will bring solutions to these problems with socio-economic and socio-cultural initiatives.

In this context, the personality development of the individual should be given immense importance and value to music education. Teachers and families should be made aware of music education given in the pre-school education period in many ways.

More time should be allocated for the music education given, and activities and organizations should be organized to ensure that these educations are more efficient and to ensure that the children in the school participate in music education.

More comprehensive research on the thesis proposal should be conducted, and these researches should be supported with postgraduate studies.

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